

SÃO PAULO'S ECOSYSTEM: FANS' POINT OF VIEW CONCERNING MARKETING STRATEGIES

Edson Coutinho da Silva¹ⁱ,
Alexandre Luzzi Las Casas²

¹University Centre FEL,
São Bernardo do Campo, Brazil
Pontifical Catholic University of São Paulo,
²São Paulo, Brazil;
Professor of Marketing at Economics and
Administration School

Abstract:

Objective: This article aims to understand and analyse which fans' attributes most interferes with their view concerning the sports ecosystem of the São Paulo Football Club for sporting events. **Methodology:** an exploratory research was carried out comprising 78 topics using the Likert scale to be administered to 215 sports fans in 3 games between February and March 2017. The analysis procedure followed three steps: (i) calculating the chi-square testes cross tables; (ii) selecting the topics which achieved less than 5% significance; (iii) and identifying that group of fans' attributes that are most similar and most divergent. **Findings:** transportation is the most critical fan attribute; gender is the second fan attribute most divergent. São Paulo's fans believe that media as the critical axis. **Conclusion:** Therefore, 1 out of 3 hypotheses was confirmed. Besides, issues as to income as well as attendance are not critical fans' attributes for the São Paulo' marketers.

Keywords: sports ecosystem; sports marketing; sports club; São Paulo football club; sports fans

1. Introduction

The sports ecosystem is basic assumptions for guiding sports managers and vendors to tackle new business as well as marketing schemes for achieving more financial funds and revenues to a sports club through a range of merchandise and services in an outcome and experience format to sports lovers (McHugh, Bronson & Watters, 2015).

ⁱ Correspondence: email dr.edson.coutinho@gmail.com

The sports managers and marketers use business and marketing principles for producing offering and benefits to fans (as customers). Even so, a sports club has no skills, expertise and competence to deal with a range of resources by itself in efficiency and efficacy way (Clemes, Brush & Collins, 2011; Maltese & Dangle, 2014). Then, inviting and involving competent and experiments stakeholders to assist and manage some activities of the process value chain is an option to design and prepare a value offer in an efficient and effective method to ensure a sports event and experience to meet the sports fans expectations (Chadwick & Thwaites, 2005).

In general, a sports ecosystem should be designed and lined up to the sports management and sports marketing in a sports club. Sports management involves people, activities, business and organisation in producing, facilitating, promoting or organising any product – goods, services, people, places or ideas – for the demand of sports fans (Bradbury & O'Boyle, 2017; Shilbury, 2009). Sports marketing aims to promote sports events, teams, products and services in sports events or entertainments (Storm, Wagner & Nielsen, 2017). Sports marketing is prescribed further as the chance for a sports club or a sports organisation to communicate their products or services in a sport-oriented context. For instance, a sports club should hire partners and sponsors for assisting and providing sports goods – clothing –, sports services for selling tickets and souvenirs, commercialising foods indoor the stadium, managing the stadium facilities, i.e., the naming rights, etc (Fullerton & Merz, 2008).

By and large, a sports ecosystem determines the actors' network for helping sports managers and sports marketers to employ activities and processes for organising a sports event (Clemes, Brush & Collins, 2011). In sum up, the sports ecosystem dimensions correspond the resources required to design the sports business and sports marketing strategies (Maltese & Dangle, 2014). But, 'how the sports ecosystem of the São Paulo Football Club is organised for a sports event, according to its fans' attributes'? This paper aims to understand and analyse which fans' attributes most infer their point of view concerning the sports ecosystem of the São Paulo Football Club (from the São Paulo city, Brazil) to organise sports events. São Paulo is the third football sports team with more number of fans in Brazil (behind of the Flamengo Sports Club and the Sport Club Corinthians) and the second São Paulo city (behind of the Sport Club Corinthians). Fans' details such as monthly salary, the form of transport, monthly attendance and gender were the four attributes used for understanding and analysing the São Paulo's ecosystem. These authors prepared a Table 1 below to introduce the São Paulo Football Club.

Table 1: Descriptions and Achievements of São Paulo

Descriptions and Achievements	São Paulo
Foundation	1935
Location or Area	South area of São Paulo city
Stadium	Morumbi Stadium, 15 kilometres from downtown
Number of Fans in Brazil	13.6 million
Brazil Leagues	Champions (6)
São Paulo Tournaments	Champions (21)
Brazil Cups	Winner (0)
Libertadores Cups (like Champions League)	Winners (3)
Sudamericana Cups (like UEFA League)	Winner (1)

Club World Cups	Winners (3)
Attendance at Stadium per Match in 2017, so far.	28.427
Uniform Sponsorship	Under Armour
Profit in 2016	US \$ 115 Million

Sources: ESPN Brasil (2017); Globo Esporte (2017); Lance & IBOPE (2017); São Paulo (2017).

2. Theoretical Background

2.1 The Function of Marketing in the Professional Sport

Marketing concepts are suffering continually evolving. Sports marketing is also undergoing profound changes which require new expertise and skills for answering to competitive challenges and fans demanding. Under these circumstances, two subjects need a reflexion: First, assessing the sports as entertainment offer and its sports ecosystem to better understand the marketing potential associated to stakeholders (events, clubs, partners, media, athletes, fans, public and private entities, etc.) (Bradbury & O'Boyle, 2017; KPMG Report, 2014; Shilbury, 2009). Second, cogitating the sports marketing as an application and strategy with specific particularities, i.e., including the importance and quality of stakeholders are critical for producing of a sporting offer as well as the emotional and captivating nature of the sporting performances (Chadwick & Thwaites, 2005).

Fullerton and Mertz (2008) describe two distinct streams in approaching the sports marketing in a sports entity. On the one hand, the marketing of sports, which adds marketing sporting events and equipment to fans and participants. This sort of sports marketing is intrinsic in the introduction of new sports such as action sports and innovative sports products. On the other hand, marketing through sports is contemplated sports as media and broadcasting or a sponsorship alternative for organisations that market consumer, and to a lesser extent, enterprise products. For Shilbury (2009), while the marketing of sports is an approach to marketing activities and processes to market goods as well as services towards to sports fans and spectators. The marketing through sports intents the promotion of non-sporting products and services at sporting events and the user of athletes (players) to support non-sports products and services.

To propose a marketing strategies model is important to overhaul the existing business model of a non-profit sports club organisation and transform this into a business marketing-oriented model of a sports ecosystem capable of delivering results against the following five axes (Collignon & Sultan, 2014; Collignon, Sultan & Santander, 2011; Leopkey & Parent, 2009): structuring marketing channels networks (members and actors); professionalising the sports club (business managers); establishing good relationship with stakeholders; dealing with actors to get resources; and managing sports brand reputation, targeting audiences through the use of various media. In summary, as Foster, O'Reilly & Dávila (2016), Shilbury (2009) and Storm, Wagner & Nielsen (2017) explain, sports clubs are using five sources of revenue to finance their organisation:

- Players (athletes), acquired from South American, Asian or African clubs, as an investment that can be sold later;

- Ticketing, which means all tickets available for watching a live match on the stadium a sporting venue;
- Partners, who control all rights for naming the arena; who produce sporting clothing, and other products or services;
- Media rights, where the media and, in special, tv broadcasters pay for broadcasting rights around the world;
- Club membership, where fans are encouraged to invest in and help to finance clubs in exchange benefits, for example, discounted in tickets, best seats at the sporting venues, etc.

2.2 Sports Fan: The Core of the Sports Marketing Strategies

Sports fan loves an active and a lived experience. Then, for attracting, even more, sports fans to events and making money, a sports club depends on a strong, a structured and an organised league, because a sports club is associated to leagues. However, for making feasible a commercial league, seven components required adjustment (Bouchet et al., 2011; Piipponen, 2011; Yoshida & James, 2010; Yoshida, 2017):

- Governance framework: need to be able to sustain and recognised by associated as an official sports federation for organising championships;
- League timing: the tournament needs to be coordinated, respecting fans, spectators, media rights and international time zone to attract more spectators around the world and positioning brand and team images and no competing with another league;
- Players: hiring and involving top players of the country or, still, the world to maximising the competition level within teams and, thus, attracting more fans, spectators and media focus;
- Marketing: developing an effective marketing plan focusing on fans, spectators and, still, quality services by sports actors (or sponsorships);
- Fans base: planning marketing strategies for engaging sports fans to join in sports event and experience, perceiving all of them as consumers;
- Arena infrastructure: qualifying all arrange of activities which are developed inside of the stadium, before, during and after sports experience;
- Match performance: improving the quality of games to capture fans, spectators, media and sponsorship interests for applying new investments.

Understanding the sports fan (as customer) behaviour as a consequence of product and service satisfaction, several attempts have been made to list the motives for sports event attendance (Norris, Wann & Zapalac, 2014; Shilbury, 2009; Yoshida, 2017): escape refers to one's diversion from usual life, some customers may also be driven by economic features, gained for example by betting, eustress is the result of obtaining excitement and stimulation in sport, sports events may also enhance one's self-esteem, group affiliation refers to event's social nature, sports customers often search for entertainment, family relates to the spending time with family, and aesthetic beauty concerns one's desire to see the artistic beauty and the grace in the sport. However, Clemes, Brush & Collins (2011) and Piipponen (2011) summarise five sports motives

considering psychological benefits that sports consumers' desire from a sports experience.

- Social interaction represents a desire for sociability as individuals are motivated to seek a sports event experience owing to opportunities for the enhancement of human relationships through external communication with other spectators, participants, friends, and family;
- Performance represents a desire for aesthetic and physical pleasure as individuals are motivated to seek a sports event experience due to opportunities to enjoy the grace, skill, and artistry of athletic movement and physiological movement;
- Excitement represents a desire for intellectual stimulation as an individual is motivated to seek a sports event experience due to opportunities for mental actions and exploration from the atmosphere created by the uncertainty of participation and competition and the spectacle of associated activities;
- Esteem represents a desire for competency as individuals are motivated to seek a sports event experience due to opportunities for achievement and challenge that produce a sense of mastery and heighten a sense of personal and collective self-esteem;
- Diversion represents a desire for mental well-being as individuals are motivated to seek a sports event experience due to opportunities to escape and remove from daily work and life routines that create stress.

2.3 Sports Ecosystem: Structuring a Sporting Offer

The sports ecosystem aims to guide marketers to propose, design and operate a marketing plan with the purpose of obtaining several sources of financial funding for undertaking new business strategies for their sports club (Foster, O'Reilly & Dávila, 2016). In summary, the sports ecosystems presented in this study aim to guide marketers to propose, design and operate a marketing plan with the purpose of obtaining several sources of financial funding for undertaking new business strategies for the sports club. Indeed, sports clubs use marketing strategies for offering benefits to fans, but for producing products and/or services marketers need to select and apply strategic resources to produce expected outcomes in an effective way (Maltese & Danglade, 2014). Then, marketing proposes involving stakeholders' competence for adding value to activities chain for promoting and handing out the best products and services to fans (Pipponen, 2011). In general, a sports ecosystem proposes a typology based on resources level considering all stakeholders and the nature interdependence among them for preparing sports events using entertainment as a concept and considering fans as consumers. Thus, even before the begin working on their marketing plan, marketers need to organise and analyse all five sources of - fans, media rights, leagues, brands and clubs.

Maltese and Danglade (2014) introduce a sports ecosystem based on analysing of sport as an entertainment. The sports ecosystem constitutes axes of a business action plan for designing, developing and delivering an offer to market made by fans. These

authors see, for instance, a league as a big event comprising matches, which are small events. For Bouchet et al (2011), sports are entertainments, since, as events, sports matches are a sort of collective celebration which brings fans together to take part in and enjoy a sport and cultural spectacle in one place. In addition, sport as entertainment involves mobilising and allocating tangible and intangible resources to meet goals and objectives. Thereby, according to Shilbury (2009), a league or a match is product and/or service which is produced, sold and delivered for a group of fans in an organised way to make them happy, cheerful and satisfied about paying for something where they can share their feeling and passion for a team. However, to deliver product and/or service to fans, a sports club requires stakeholders to deliver these in an efficient manner. Collignon & Sultan (2014) argue that a sports ecosystem focuses on four components: fan interfaces, strategic heart, strategic resources and value chain.

Thus, four sports ecosystems were analysed to design our sports ecosystem model. The first sports ecosystem was presented in a report published by KPMG. The sports ecosystem created by KPMG (2014) focuses on two aspects: sports transparency and professionalism coupled with growing awareness of all stakeholders within and across various segments; and producing a winning sports team. Bearing in mind the transparency, professionalism and a winning team, as the three key objectives of KPMG's sports ecosystem, seven axes were designed for achieving these goals: sports governance; talent scouting & training of players; sports infrastructures; training of trainers; sports equipment (goods); leagues and tournaments; and performance incentives.

Rundh and Gottfridsson (2015) created a sports ecosystem which aims to deliver a sports event using actors for intervening and interacting with each other to produce an expected offer based on entertainment, leisure and experience concepts. They understand that the actors' network is the key, the challenge and the opportunity to create a value proposition for a sports event, because sports clubs have no skills to deal with business, marketing and consumers, as sports and non-sports companies do. Thus, Rundh and Gottfridsson structured their sports ecosystem from ten dimensions: sports fans, partners & sponsors, business suppliers, the communities (managing the external infrastructure around the stadium), tv broadcasting and media, federation and confederation, the volunteers (to assist and guide fans), sports club, the stadium, and athletes.

The third sports ecosystem was schemed by Maltese and Danglade (2014). The sports ecosystem designed by them aims to analyse sports as entertainment to introduce business and marketing perspectives required for planning sports event. They transposed to the business environment the ecological notion of an ecosystem, which is formed by two elements interacting with the environment (biotope) and the living beings that occupy it (biocenosis). They attempted to operationalise the concepts of networks, alliance, and virtual enterprise. On the one hand, biotope may be characterised by an event venue, i.e., stadium, arena, natural spaces and fans; and on the other hand, biocenosis means stakeholders, i.e., athletes, sports institutions, sponsor of a stadium – naming rights –, partners, suppliers and media.

The last sports ecosystem was designed by Collignon and Sultan (2014), aiming at a good cash flow management for a sports club. Their inspirations and references came from American sports, European football leagues and Grand Slam tennis championships, as Wimbledon in London, England. For them, a sports club plays a relevant role in the sports ecosystem because clubs understand the need to pay special attention to five elements: (i) fans expectations: spending their money, (ii) media: buying rights to broadcast matches for an audience of fans, (iii) brands in the sports area: selecting the right partner clubs, leagues and athletes, (iv) leagues: organising the seasons and they play an intermediary role in flowing revenues to clubs, (v) clubs: getting revenues and profits from ticketing, selling licensed products, sponsorships and media rights.

For us, a sports ecosystem should have business and marketing concepts embedded into it to ensure fan satisfaction, revenues, and profits to a sports club. Sport is inspiring, engaging, immersive, emotion evoking and rapidly growing the revenues and profits; however, through a platform of market and customer orientation, it is possible to go further. Capturing the essence of understanding sport as an event, introduced by Maltese and Danglade (2014); the sense of professionalism showed by KPMG Reports (2014) related to organisation standard; the concerns about actors' network depicted by Rundth and Gottfridsson (2015); observing the sport as an opportunity for a sports club to make money, as presented by Collignon and Sultan (2014); and, still, analysing the Brazilian context regarding the football culture, sports club organisation, fans and media, we have decided to line up a sports ecosystem in which it was possible to take advantage of each value proposition showed by every author above. Therefore, our sports ecosystem aims to encourage a sports professional to design a sports event in synergy with stakeholders to offer an enjoyable sports experience taking into consideration the customer orientation principles to provide revenues and profit for the sports club. Thus, seven axes were designed to achieve these goals, see Figure 1 and Table 2.

Figure 1: Sports Ecosystem Dimensions

Source: Authors

Table 2: Sports Ecosystem Dimensions

Dimensions	Descriptions
Leagues (Confederations or Federations)	Responsible for organising the seasons, leagues and tournaments. However, in most cases they also play an intermediary role in flowing revenues to clubs, particularly the media rights money; then, the leagues perform three relevant functions: organising competitions, creating valuable events, and structuring media rights tenders (Bradbury & O'Boyle, 2017; Shilbury, 2009; Storm, Wagner & Nielsen, 2017);
Goods Suppliers	On the one hand, they are investors who put money into the business for promoting their brand, images or products and services through a sports club. On the other hand, they may, also, associate their brands with a sports club and provide uniforms and sports goods for them, as t-shirts, shorts, shoes, cap, jacket, etc, and non-sports goods: foods, drinks, toys, etc (Fullerton & Merz, 2008; Giroux, Pons & Maltese, 2017);
Fans' Engagement	Sports clubs should create a customer-oriented strategy to transfer their excitations and passions for spending their money to buy packages of pay- tv, tickets for games, products and services associated with sports club, and to become a member (Norris, Wann & Zapalac, 2014; Piipponen, 2011; Yoshida & James, 2010; Yoshida, 2017);
Stadium (or Arena)	It involves facilities, naming rights, architecture, advertising inside the stadium, etc., The sports clubs can make money using several sorts of events (Leopkey & Parent, 2009);
Club Management	Responsible for: (i) designing its offers and benefits (embedding its value proposition and experience) articulated to the expectations of different targets, as fans, supporters, enthusiasts and followers, (ii) managing their flow of money from ticketing, selling licensed products, sponsorships, and media rights, as well as ensuring the quality of the event value chain, pre, during and post-game, (iii) and purchasing and selling athletes, ensuring infrastructure and staff, executing governance strategies and managing its brands (Ratten, 2016; Foster, O'Reilly, Dávila, 2016);
Partnerships & Sponsorships	It aims to support fans in sports events (paying for private and public transportation), guide and provide safety for the fans inside the stadium, restaurants, parking, etc. In other words, partners are co-creators of the value chain offering facilities inside and outside the venue (Amorim & Almeida, 2015; Chadwick & Thwaites, 2005);
Media & tv Broadcasting	Responsible for buying rights of matches for television for an audience of fans, and offering to passionate fans an alternative platform, as cable tv, pay- tv, websites, social networks and apps (Burden & Li, 2009; McHugh, Bronson & Watters, 2015).

Sources: Authors

2.4 Issues that Interfere with the Sports Ecosystem

According to Maltese & Danglade (2014) and Rundh & Gottfridsson (2015) state that some groups of variables may interfere with a sports ecosystem. For Shilbury (2009), the first group is comprised of the external environment as demography and social trends, economic issues, technology trends, political legislation, natural and sustainable concerns, etc. According to Bradbury & O'Boyle (2017), the second group is composed of the internal environment such as resources, competencies, capacity of providing services, consumer-oriented culture of the club, departments' performance, suppliers and outsourcing, sponsorships, marketing mix (product, price, place and promotion) and public. For Rundh & Gottfridsson (2015) and Yoshida (2017), the third group approaches the fans (as consumer) to answer the issues such as "Who are the fans?", "Why do they buy a specific sport product?", "When and where do they buy the product or service?", "What does the consumption entail in terms of pre- and post-event activities?", and "How do fans use the product so that a complete specification of them can be lined up to their expectation?" These variables may infer in the performance as well as in the fans' perceptions regarding a sports ecosystem. Thus, we chose four variables to carry out this research:

- Monthly salary (or incomes): fans may be encouraged to or discouraged from the consumption of goods and services offered by a sports club due to their wages (e.g., a demographic detail);
- Gender: men and women have different consumption habits and preferences. Men tend to be more fanatic than women (in theory). Thus, understanding their

profile may assist marketers to fit an offer for each group (another demographic detail);

- Form of transport: the transportation system is a relevant information that impacts in the negative and positive way in the sports ecosystem since a sports club depends on the stakeholders and partners from the public (bus, train, and subway) and the private (taxi, Uber and car parking facilities) sectors to carry out a sports event in its stadium (e.g., internal environment detail);
- Monthly attendance: understanding when and how many times the fans buy tickets and consume goods and services can help the sports marketers know their habits and consumption behaviour (e.g., a consumer behaviour detail).

Therefore, the monthly salary, monthly attendance, form of transport and gender may provide a sports marketer distinct views concerning the sports ecosystem. On the one hand, a fan who has a high income can value or criticise an ecosystem's dimension more than others. On the other hand, a fan who has a regular attendance in the stadium may think in a different way in relation to those who go to the arena once a month. Our proposal describes these contents in this study in order to discover what is the attribute which more interferes in the fans' opinion. By and large, each attribute can change the fans' perceptions of the ecosystem's dimensions.

3. Research Methodology

This research has the purpose of approaching the sports ecosystem in three of the most prominent sports clubs in the State of São Paulo, Brazil. Thus, this exploratory study aims to understand and analyse which fans' attributes most infer their point of view concerning of the sports ecosystem of the São Paulo Football Club (from the São Paulo city, Brazil) to organise sports events. Three hypotheses were described to infer the results: (h1) transportation is the fan' attribute which more infers since the public transport is chaotic in São Paulo city; (h2) monthly salary is the second one, because of the economic crisis in Brazil; (h3) and the stadium is the sport ecosystem's axis most critical, due to the venue has old facilities (the stadium was built in the 1960s and has no general standards of safety and comfort of a modern stadium, as recommend by FIFA). These authors designed and prepared a sports ecosystem (as shown in Figure 1/Table 2) to perform this study, since the four models analysed do not reflect the sports club reality in Brazil. Also, a pre-test was carried out with 10 sports fans some weeks before collecting process to see the fans' reactions. The five sports ecosystems were presented to these 10 sports fans: the four which were designed by the authors above, and that one organised by these authors. None of them had any sort of identification, and all of them had a description of each axis. The question proposed the fans was: 'what do sports ecosystem was most appropriate to understand the Brazilian sports clubs?'. At the large, 5 choose the sports ecosystem prepared by us, 2 from Collignon & Sultan's ecosystem, 1 from Maltase & Danglade's ecosystem, and 1 from Rundh & Gottfridsson's ecosystem. None of them chooses the KPMG's ecosystem. They argued that a model using seven dimensions designed by us became much more accessible to observe the

proposal of each axis for the sports business and marketing. The fans' opinions assisted us in organising a questionnaire to collect data taking into consideration a considerable number of fans.

Apropos the data and results reports, a questionnaire with 78 topics/statements (see Table 3) – related to the sports ecosystem perspective was designed by these researchers considering five Likert levels (1) totally disagree; (2) partly disagree; (3) I cannot answer; (4) agree; (5) totally agree. Besides, four fan's personal details were demanded by the fans in order to know their attributes, for instance, gender, monthly salary (with base on the minimum monthly wages in Brazil), monthly attendance to the stadium (1, 2-3, 4-6) and transportation they use to go to the stadium (own vehicle, public transport or private transportation, as Uber, taxi, etc.). These questions were included on the top of the instrument. Generally explaining, 78 topics were presented in questionnaires and fans should select one of the five levels in the rating scale for each statement, spread in seven dimensions: (i) league: 10 statements; (ii) stadium: 12 statements; (iii) goods suppliers: 13 statements; (iv) fans' engagement: 20 statements; (v) club management: 12 statements; (vi) partnerships and sponsorships: 6 statements; and (vii) media & tv broadcasting: 5 statements.

Table 3: Topics of the Questionnaire

Leagues & Tournaments	Stadium (or Arena)	Goods Suppliers
01. Clear rules	11. Point of sale (ticketing)	23. Fans buy illegal goods
02. Calendars for matches	12. Comfortable seats and toilets	24. Discount to fan-members
03. Calendars for tv	13. Car parking structure	25. Assortment of models and sizes
04. Quality of games	14. Snack bar or restaurants	26. 3 goods per year
05. Balanced teams	15. Prioritising fan-members	27. Licensed club stores
06. Media coverage	16. Space (or area) for the disabled	28. Sports stores
07. tv broadcasting to Europe	17. Partnership with public sector	29. Few options of goods
08. 15,000 fans on average	18. Safety for fans	30. Vintage uniforms
09. Fan's regular audience	19. Guides to help fans	31. Sponsor stamped on club goods
10. Cash prizes similar to Europe	20. Expensive tickets	32. Stores in stadium
Fans' Engagement	21. Kiosks to sell products	33. Celebration uniforms
36. Reading books and newspapers	22. Kiosks to become members	34. Gifting family and friends
37. Collecting photos and posters	Club Management	35. Customising goods
38. Pay- tv subscription	56. Business management concepts	Partnerships & Sponsorships
39. Visiting the trophy room	57. Transparent management	68. Making investments in the club
40. Main athletes and starting line-up	58. Monetarily responsible concepts	69. Adding value to club brand
41. Visiting club website every week	59. Customer-oriented principles	70. Having few incentive policies
42. Attending training	60. Paying the bills	71. Risk for company's brand
43. Following social networks	61. Dealing with partners	72. Improving quality of products
44. Visiting club stores	62. Positive image for investors	73. Enhancing relationship with fans
45. Having historical T-shirts	63. Producing own athletes	
46. Attending opponent's stadium	64. Receiving criticisms	
47. Encouraging relatives	65. Social responsibility plan	
48. Encouraging co-workers	66. Relationship with fans	
49. Wearing T-shirts on match day	67. Using marketing strategies	
50. Seeing T-shirt in another State	Media	
51. Seeing T-shirt in another country	74. Valuing the national league	
52. Mock friends	75. Paying well to cover games	
53. Watching sports tv programmes	76. Prioritising clubs on media	
54. Choosing the team in FIFA video game	77. Promoting naming rights on media	
55. Accessing YouTube to watch the goals	78. Interfering on league calendars.	

Source: Authors

Overall, 215 questionnaires were administered to sports fans between February and March 2017. To use the instrument, these researchers selected three matches of each

football sports club, in which, three criteria were relevant: (i) administered to ordinary fans; (ii) carried out only inside the club stadium; and (iii) all 78 statements should be answered. Table 4 presents the Who, Where, When, and What, related to the administration process. The data collection took place inside and around the Morumbi Stadium before the games and took roughly 3 hours per match. However, only 215 questionnaires were obtained from the São Paulo's fans. The limitation in obtaining all questionnaires answered is because, São Paulo's fans did not want to help us answering them. The administration process was the same in all matches. In other words, 360 instruments were printed to be administered on the day of the three matches. Unfortunately, São Paulo had the fewest instruments answered, according to expectation.

Table 4: Matches, Places, Date and Tournament

São Paulo's Games	Place	Date	League or Tournament
São Paulo vs. Santo André	Morumbi Stadium	5 th March 2017	São Paulo Tournament.
São Paulo vs. Ituano	Morumbi Stadium	18 th March 2017	São Paulo Tournament.
São Paulo vs Corinthians	Morumbi Stadium	26 th March 2017	São Paulo Tournament

Source: Authors

The software Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) was used to perform the analysis of the results in three steps: first, a general report applying chi-square tests from cross tables between the four groups of fans' attributes and sports ecosystem topics; then, the selecting process of the issues which achieved the significance $\leq 0,05$ (5%); and finally, observing and settling on which profile of each group of fans' attributes that agreed or disagreed with other profiles on a given topic have reached more than 95% of statistical significance. The analysis and explanation of the results will be introduced in four tables, see Tables 5 to 8 below which were designed respecting the analysis procedure. Throughout the report of the findings, relevant fans' attributes are pointed out to indicate the fans' characteristics and their implications for fans' choices.

4. Results and Findings

4.1 Monthly Salary versus Sports Ecosystem

According to the 78 topics described in the questionnaires collected from 215 São Paulo's fans, only 13 topics have a statistical significance of $\leq 0,05$ concerning "monthly salary versus sports ecosystem". The group of fans was split into three categories of fans' profile (according to their monthly income, having as base the monthly minimum salary in Brazil): zero (students who depend economically on their relatives), 1 - 4, and 5 - 8, as shown in column \$ MS, Table 5. Looking into the seven dimensions designed by these authors, only five pointed out some disagreement among the fans. The goods suppliers and club management axes had no topic cited. On the leagues' axis, those who have Zero income tend to disagree with the statement "leagues or tournaments drew the attention of the media to cover the games". For them, the foreign leagues have many more games broadcasted on tv than the local or national leagues, including the Internet media. The broadcasting of the European leagues on tv has impacted on the sales of the

European clubs' t-shirts in Brazil. According to UOL & Netshoes (2017), Barcelona is the tenth club which sells more t-shirts in Brazil, and the first one, excluding Brazilian clubs, followed by Real Madrid (2nd), Bayer München (3rd), Chelsea (4th), Manchester City (5th), Manchester United (6th), Paris Saint-Germain (7th), Juventus (8th), Milan (9th), and Dortmund (10th). In 2017, São Paulo Football Club was the second club of the State of São Paulo – behind Corinthians – and, the third in Brazil – behind Corinthians and Flamengo – which has more matches broadcasted on tv.

Table 5: Monthly Salary (or Incomes) vs Sports Ecosystem

Leagues & Tournaments	Sig <= 0,05	(\$) MS	A D	Fans' Engagement	Sig <= 0,05	(\$) MS	A D
06. Media coverage	0,007	Zero	D	39. Visiting the trophy room	0,026	1 – 4	D
Stadium	Sig <= 0,05	(\$) MS	A D	52. Mock friends	0,043	1 – 4	D
11. Point of sale (ticketing)	0,011	5 – 8	A	54. Choosing the team in FIFA video game	0,048	Zero	A
17. Partnership with public sector	0,029	Zero	A	55. Accessing YouTube to watch the goals	0,037	Zero	A
18. Safety for fans	0,017	1 – 4	D	Partnership & Sponsorship	Sig <= 0,05	(\$) MS	A D
19. Guides to help fans	0,002	Zero	D	68. Making investments in the club	0,027	1 - 4	A
Media	Sig <= 0,05	(\$) MS	A D	70. Having few incentive policies	0,013	Zero	A
74. Valuing the national league	0,015	1 – 4	D				
75. Paying well to cover games	0,042	5 – 8	D				

Caption 1: (\$) MS = Monthly Salary with 3 options: Zero (0), 1 – 4, and 5 – 8 Minimum Salary = US\$ 280,00 (roughly).

Caption 2: A = Tending to agree regarding other 2 groups, and D = Tending to disagree regarding other 2 groups.

Source: Authors

Regarding the stadium, the idea was to understand how São Paulo Football Club supports its fans before, during and after the games. Those who earn between 5 and 8 monthly minimum salaries agree that the number of box offices which sell tickets is enough, both physical and virtual. Although, those who earn between 1 and 4 monthly salaries have a different point of view concerning safety to fans, because the club cannot ensure safety outside the venue. Those fans who depend on their relatives agree about the partnership with the public sector since most of them take public transportation to go to the Morumbi Stadium. But they do not share the same point of view regarding guides assisting fans in the venue. According to them, this type of service has a low quality. The stadium is a relevant space that a sports club may use to improve the relationship with their fans, and to dialogue with them. A good relationship may ensure new alternatives of revenues and profits for a club. Thus, São Paulo's marketers need require to solve this problem and to undertake new services.

Concerning the fans' engagement, four aspects were pointed out as significant, according to São Paulo's fans: visiting the club's website every week, mocking friends, choosing the team on FIFA video game, and accessing YouTube to watch the matches and goals of the team. On the one hand, those who receive between 1 and 4 minimum salaries disagree regarding visiting the club's website every week and mock friends when the opponent sports team failed in a given match. On the other hand, those who get no salary (zero) choose São Paulo when they play FIFA video game and access

YouTube to seek news and information about the club. This report introduces significant subjects: fans who have a job, do not usually access the club's website, probably they prefer another sort of media, and fans who have no jobs tend to access the digital platforms to communicate with the club. The sports club requires analysing the media habits of fans to undertake new communication strategies to line up their services offer to fans.

Media and partnership & sponsorship are the last two axes. With respect to the media, both fans who earn 1 to 4, and 5 to 8 minimum wages, disagree, each one on a specific topic. The fans who live on 1 to 4 monthly wages do not agree about the preference of the media for national or local leagues. For instance, taking into consideration the four sports channels on cable tv: Sport tv, ESPN, Fox Sports and Interactive Sport, all of them have a sports platform oriented to foreign leagues, such as Bundesliga (Germany), La Liga (Spain), Serie A (Italy), Ligue 1 (France) and Premier League (England). The Globo channel broadcasts the leading leagues in Brazil. Also, the media does not pay well – if compared to the European leagues – to broadcast the matches on tv, according to São Paulo's fans. Concerning the partnership & sponsorship, the fans who receive between 1 and 4 salaries believe that companies have invested money in São Paulo Football Club, and those who have no monthly salary, also think that there are government incentives to encourage new investment in the sports clubs. These justifies, for instance, the number of companies 'stamped' on the t-shirts and shorts, - at least three were observed in São Paulo Football Club's uniforms in 2017.

4.2 Transportation versus Sports Ecosystem

Table 6: Transportation vs. Sports Ecosystem

Leagues & Tournaments	Sig <= 0,05	Trans.	A D	Stadium	Sig <= 0,05	Trans.	A D
10. Cash prizes similar to Europe	0,031	OwV	D	11. Point of sale (ticketing)	0,020	OwV	D
Goods Suppliers	Sig <= 0,05	Trans.	A D	12. Comfortable seats and toilets	0,005	PuT	A
25. Assortment of models and sizes	0,000	PuT	A	13. Car parking structure	0,005	OwV	D
27. Licensed club stores	0,049	OwV	A	16. Space (or area) for the disabled	0,001	OwV	A
Club Management	Sig <= 0,05	Trans.	A D	20. Expensive tickets	0,044	PuT	A
58. Monetarily responsible concepts	0,005	OwV	D	Fans' Engagement	Sig <= 0,05	Trans.	A D
60. Paying the bills	0,001	PuT	A	44. Visiting club stores	0,000	PuT	A
62. Positive image for investors	0,030	PuT	A	49. Wearing T-shirts on match day	0,015	OwV	D
63. Producing own athletes	0,025	PuT	D	53. Watching sports tv programmes	0,020	PrT	D
Partnership & Sponsorship	Sig <= 0,05	Trans.	A D	Media	Sig <= 0,05	Trans.	A D
68. Making investments in the club	0,003	OwV	D	75. Paying well to cover games	0,025	OwV	D

Caption 1: Trans. = Transportation with 3 options: PuT = Public Transportation; PrT = Private Transportation; OwV = Own Vehicle.

Caption 2: A = Tending to agree regarding other 2 groups, and D = Tending to disagree regarding other 2 groups.

Source: Authors

Combining the categories of “form of transport” and “sports ecosystem”, from a total of 78 subjects, 17 have statistical significance of less than 5%. With regard to the category form of “transport versus sports ecosystem”, only 17 topics have a statistical significance over $\leq 5\%$. To depict the category of transportation, three groups were created: public transportation (PuT), private transportation (PrT), e.g., taxi, Uber, etc., and own vehicle (OwV). As approached heretofore, the idea is to describe which group has a different opinion in relation to the other two groups, as shown in column ‘Trans’, seen Table 6. It is relevant to mention that 121 out of 215 fans have their own vehicle to go to the matches, of which 82 were males, and 39 were females, and most of them receive between 5 and 8 minimum monthly salaries. Under the transportation perspective, all seven axes of the sports ecosystem were pointed out. Apropos of the leagues, the OwV group does not believe that the value of cash prizes given to winner team is fair, using the European leagues as a reference. For instance, the cash prizes in 2017 of the Confederation of Brazilian Football (CBF) for the winner of the Brazilian League added up to roughly US \$ 5.5 million, much less than European leagues, that were around US \$ 25 million.

The stadium is the axis which has more conflict among fans. The OwV group does not agree that the São Paulo provides plenty of points of sale as well as parking lots. For this group, parking is extremely relevant, since they go to the stadium in their own vehicles to watch the games and the club does not provide private parking. Thus, fans are parking their cars on the street or in private parking lots that are not licensed and recognised by the club. Furthermore, the venue is located near a famous shantytown in São Paulo named as ‘Paraisópolis’, which discourages many fans from parking their cars in the street, especially in the games that take place on weekdays (in the evening). This same group agrees that the club provides space for disabled people to watch the games. The PuT group agrees about the comfortable seats as well as the bathrooms, also, this same group expresses a ‘negative’ view on the fact that the tickets are very expensive, considering the monthly salary of an ordinary fan.

Two topics described on the “goods suppliers” and another four on the “club management” axes brought up some divergence among the fans. The OwV group has a different opinion from the other two groups since they usually buy products in licensed club's stores. Likewise, the PuT group presumes that Under Armour has provided several goods to fans. For the OwV group the club has not been managed in a financially responsible way, as they expected. In other words, the club spends much more money than earns (ticketing, tv rights, etc) and receives investments from sponsorships. The PuT group has two distinct points of view related to three topics: these fans see that managers have paid the bills correctly, including athletes, ordinary employees, etc., equally, the club has enhanced the institutional image of the companies which have invested in the club. However, they argue that the club has not produced relevant athletes as previously done. This club found out famous players who performed in relevant sports clubs in Europe as well as in Brazilian football team in World Cups, such as Cafú, Kaká, Denilson, and Leonardo. Recently, São Paulo Football Club has spent more money on hiring athletes than producing them.

“Fans' engagement”, “partnership and sponsorship”, and “the media” have topics which achieved a certain level of disagreement. The PuT group is the one who visits club's stores more often, but they are not the ones who buy the most, as it was seen. The OwV group does not usually wear the club's t-shirt when they are watching or listening to a match, and, also the PrT group does not watch sports tv programmes to follow the news regarding the club. According to the OwV group, partners and sponsors have not made investments in the club as they expected. i.e., the amount of money has not been enough considering the benefits which companies achieve in terms of profits when they associate their brands with the club. Still about money, this same group does not recognise that the media have not paid a relevant amount of money for broadcasting some games of the leagues in which the club takes part.

4.3 Monthly Attendance versus Sports Ecosystem

Table 7: Monthly Attendance at Stadium vs Sports Ecosystem

Leagues & Tournaments	Sig <= 0,05	M.A.	A D	Fans' Engagement	Sig <= 0,05	M.A.	A D
09. Fan's regular audience	0,013	2 – 3	A	36. Reading books and newspapers	0,032	1	D
10. Cash prizes similar to Europe	0,023	4 – 6	A	37. Collecting photos and posters	0,001	1	D
Goods Suppliers	Sig <= 0,05	M.A.	A D	38. Pay- tv subscription	0,000	4 – 6	A
27. Licensed club stores	0,042	2 – 3	A	44. Visiting club stores	0,002	1	A
28. Sports stores	0,031	1	D	45. Having historical T-shirts	0,019	1	D
Media	Sig <= 0,05	M.A.	A D	46. Attending opponent's stadium	0,007	1	D
74. Valuing the national league	0,047	2 – 3	D	47. Encouraging relatives	0,025	1	A
				53. Watching sports tv programmes	0,023	4 – 6	D

Caption 1: A.M. = Monthly Attendance at Stadium with 3 options: 1 time per month; 2 – 3 times per month; and 4 – 6 times per month.
 Caption 2: A = Tending to agree regarding other 2 groups, and D = Tending to disagree regarding other 2 groups.

Source: Authors

Concerning “monthly attendance” and “sports ecosystem”, only four dimensions and 13 topics reached statistical significance of $\leq 0,05$. Three categories were delineated for examining the monthly attendance to matches in Morumbi Stadium: 1, 2 – 3 and 4 – 6, as presented in Table 7. Looking at “monthly salary” and “transportation”: about 46% (98) of fans who watch the matches in Morumbi Stadium earn between 1 and 4 minimum monthly salaries. 70 out of these 98 fans go to the stadium between 2 and 3 times; and roughly 56% (121) of the fans use their vehicle to attend the stadium; in addition, 83 out of these 121 fans go to the stadium once a month. Curiously, the fans who use private transportation to go to Morumbi Stadium are those who have less attendance at the games. In other words, the fans' profile may be defined as: fans who go to the stadium once a month 67% (145 out of 215) drive their vehicle to the venue, and earn between 1 and 4 minimum monthly salaries.

Concerning the leagues, the fans who attend the stadium between 2 and 3 times have a point of view that the national leagues and tournaments which are organised by the Brazilian Confederation and São Paulo Federation have their attention, either in the stadium or on tv. Also, fans who watch the matches in the stadium believe that the cash

prizes given to winning teams are suitable to the European leagues. Apropos of the goods suppliers, fans who go to the stadium between 2 and 3 times a month usually buy their products and souvenirs in licensed club's stores. The same way, those fans who attend the stadium once a month do not usually buy their official goods in sports stores. Hence, both groups of fans tend to buy their São Paulo's products (t-shirts, jackets, caps, etc.), in licensed club's stores. Regarding the media, the group of fans who has a monthly attendance between 2 and 3 does not agree that the Brazilian media value the national league. For them, the sports channels have broadcasted much more matches from European leagues than national leagues, in particular, the cable tv channels.

Regarding interaction with fans, eight topics were noticed as conflicting. The fans who go to the venue once a month and between 4 and 6 times stood out on this axis. The fans who attend once a month disagree on four topics, but agree in other two. For instance, this group of fans has no habit of reading newspapers and books nor collecting pictures and posters related to the club's achievements or idol athletes. This same group of fans does not have old fashioned (or vintage) t-shirts and buy souvenirs from the club. Also, they disagree about going to the opponent's club's stadium to support São Paulo Football Club to win a rival team. However, these fans usually go to club's stores and have encouraged family members to be a fan. The group who attends the club between 4 and 6 times monthly subscribes to pay- tv to follow the sports news, and they like to watch sports tv programmes to get updated on their team news. In summary, this axis indicates that the fans who attend the stadium once a month have no loyalty (as a consumer who buys goods and has a strong relationship with the club) and, those who to go to the stadium between 4 and 6 times tend to watch sports tv news. Encouraging fans to become a member and using cable tv as a means to approach the fans are two marketing strategies that the club should address to achieve more fans.

4.4 Gender versus Sports Ecosystem

Table 8: Gender vs Sports Ecosystems

Leagues	Sig <= 0,05	Gender	A D	Fans' Engagement	Sig <= 0,05	Gender	A D
01. Clear rules	0,001	M	A	36. Reading books and newspapers	0,039	F	D
04. Quality of games	0,024	F	D	40. Main athletes and starting line-up	0,000	F	D
05. Balanced teams	0,005	M	A	52. Mock friends	0,009	M	A
09. Fan's regular audience	0,000	F	D	53. Watching sports tv programmes	0,001	M	A
10. Cash prizes similar to Europe	0,001	M	D	55. Accessing YouTube to watch the goals	0,018	F	D
Goods Suppliers	Sig <= 0,05	Gender	A D	Club Management	Sig <= 0,05	Gender	A D
25. Assortment of models and sizes	0,006	M	D	63. Producing own athletes	0,014	F	D
30. Vintage uniforms	0,016	F	D	Media	Sig <= 0,05	Gender	A D
35. Customising goods	0,038	M	A	76. Prioritising clubs on media	0,012	M	A
				78. Interfering on league calendars.	0,011	M	A

Caption 1: Gender = M: Male; and F = Female.

Caption 2: A = Tending to agree regarding the other group, and D = Tending to disagree regarding the other group.

Source: Authors

In respect of the gender of fans and sports ecosystem, 16 topics were highlighted in five axes with more than 95% of statistical significance, as can be seen in Table 8. A total of 152 men and 63 women took part in this research. Both men and women usually go to the stadium once a month; both live on 1 – 4 minimum salaries; and both drive their vehicle to go to the stadium, i.e., 39 (out of 63) women, and 82 (out of 152) men. As to the men, they tend to agree on the topic of clear rules because in their point of view the leagues and championships rules are clarified by the media, even if you agree or not; and they also agree about balanced teams, since a club does not usually win a league for several years in a row. For instance, six different sports teams have won the Brazilian league in the last ten years. However, this same group of fans disagrees about cash prizes being equivalent to the ones in European leagues, because, in their opinion, it is not true. Women tend to think in a different way about the quality of games, they believe that the quality is not comparable to European leagues, for example. The league does not usually have their audience every week.

Concerning the goods suppliers, men agree about the alternative of customisation, e.g., it is possible to write the fan's name on the t-shirt. But they do not agree regarding the offer of an assortment of models and sizes to buy in the sports stores. Apropos the vintage uniforms, women do not usually buy a uniform which remembers the achievement of São Paulo from twenty or thirty years ago. On the fans' engagement axis, women do not have the habit of (i) reading newspapers and books of the club, (ii) knowing who the main athletes and those who start the games every match are and (iii) accessing YouTube to see the goals or a performance of an athlete. Men love mocking friends who support the opponent team, and they also watch sports tv programmes to know about the news in relation to games, athletes, leagues, etc. Apropos of the role of São Paulo as a creator of new athletes, the women disagree, because, in their opinion, the club has hired more athletes than encouraged young athletes to become professionals. Finally, the men believe that the media prioritise one club over the others on tv, newspapers, and the internet, still, they tend to agree that the media interfere on the league calendars to achieve their interests instead of teams' and fans' interests.

5. Conclusions

The sports ecosystem has the function of assisting sports managers and marketers to propose, design and perform sports marketing strategies with the purpose of obtaining more revenue and profit sources for undertaking new business on sports clubs through the customer-fan journey or customer-fan experience. The sports club needs to consider the sports ecosystem to perform marketing strategies in order to produce new benefits to fans. However, for producing products and services, sports marketers need to select and carry out strategic resources to provide an expected outcome with efficacy, also inviting and involving stakeholders, as partners and sponsors, to take part in the process of producing, charging, delivering and promoting the offer to an audience of fans. The sports ecosystem establishes the function of stakeholders as well as the

interdependence among all of them to design a sports event, experience, and entertainment based on business and marketing management which understands fans as customers.

This study had the objective of understanding as well as analysing which fans' attributes most affects their point of view concerning the sports ecosystem of São Paulo Football Club for sports events. Thus, after successive analyses, transportation is the fan's attribute which most interferes in the fan's point of view taking into consideration the sports ecosystem's dimensions, since Morumbi Stadium is located in an area of difficult access to public and private transportation. Overall, 17 out of 78 statements showed some divergent opinions, such as the 'stadium' (with 5 statements) is the most critical dimension, followed by 'club management' (4), 'fans' engagement' (3), 'goods suppliers' (2) and 'leagues'. "Partnership and sponsorship" and "the media" had only one topic pointed out. Thus, the first hypothesis was confirmed, in other words, the transportation is the fans' attribute that most affects their view. But the second hypothesis was not verified since the gender had 16 statements, followed by monthly attendance and monthly salary that were 'tied', then, both attributes obtained 13 statements. These authors supposed that monthly salary would be the second most important attribute given the current economic situation in Brazil. Apropos of the gender, men and women expressed distinct points of view in relation to some topics in the São Paulo's ecosystem. Also, issues as to salary and attendance are not critical variables for a sports manager or marketer.

Examining the São Paulo's ecosystem dimensions and the four fans' attributes, the third hypothesis was not confirmed, since the stadium axis supposed to be the most critical all of the axes. However, media & tv broadcasting (6 out of 20 = 30%) is the dimension accepted as the most critical, followed by: fans' engagement (20 out of 80 = 25%), leagues (9 out of 40 = 22,5%), the stadium (9 out of 48 = 19%), goods suppliers (7 out of 52 = 13,5%), partnerships and sponsorships (3 out of 24 = 12,5%), and club management (5 out of 48 = 10,5%). Thus, the stadium is not a critical dimension regarding monthly attendance and gender. Nonetheless, the stadium axis needs to take into consideration the design of the service being offered, since the venue was a relevant aspect when we analysed the fans' monthly salary and the form of transport they take to go to the stadium. Then, it is possible to conclude that: (i) São Paulo's fans drive their own vehicle to go to the stadium to watch the matches; (ii) students who depend economically on their relatives and who earn between 1 and 4 monthly salaries are those who cause more conflicts; (iii) apropos the gender attribute, women disagree in all aspects concerning all topics and dimensions that they gave their point of view. In other words, for women, São Paulo Football Club has the following critical dimensions: leagues, goods suppliers, fans' engagement and club management. Nevertheless, managing a sports team as São Paulo Football Club is not an easy job. For being a large sports club, its facilities and value chain are complex, after all, São Paulo is one of the biggest sports clubs in Brazil.

About the Authors

Name: Edson Coutinho da Silva

Institution / Affiliation: University Centre FEI, São Bernardo do Campo, Brazil.

Address: Rua Humberto de Alencar Castelo Branco, 3792 – São Bernardo do Campo, São Paulo, Brazil – 09850-901.

Country: Brazil

Biography Summary: Postdoctoral in Marketing from Pontifical Catholic University of São Paulo; Postdoc in Marketing, University of São Paulo.

Doctor in Social Science at Pontifical Catholic University of São Paulo; and Doctor in Public Health from Federal University of São Paulo.

ORCID: 0000-0002-9595-5963

Name: Alexandre Luzzi Las Casas

Institution / Affiliation: Pontifical Catholic University of São Paulo, São Paulo, Brazil; Professor of Marketing at Economics and Administration School.

Address: Rua Ministro Godoy, 969 – Perdizes, São Paulo, Brazil – 05015-901.

Biography Summary: Postdoctoral in Marketing, Portuguese Catholic University, Porto, Portugal.

Doctor of Administration from Getulio Vargas Foundation

ORCID: 0000-0003-2098-0969

References

1. Amorim, J. G. B. & Almeida, V. M. C. (2015). The Effect of Simultaneous Sponsorship of Rival Football Teams. *Brazilian Administration Review*. 12(1), 63-87.
2. Bouchet, P., Bodet, G., Bernache-Assollant, I. & Kada F. (2011). Segmenting Sports Spectators: Construction and Preliminary Validation of The Sporting Event Experience Search (SEES) Scale. *Sports Management Review*, 14, 42-53.
3. Bradbury, T. & O'Boyle, I. (2017) *Understanding Sports Management: International Perspectives*. New York, USA: Routledge.
4. Burden, W. & Li, M. (2009). Minor League Baseball: Exploring the Growing Interest in Outsourced Sports Marketing. *Sports Marketing Quarterly*, 18, 139-149.
5. Chadwick, S. & Thwaites, D. (2005). Management Sports Sponsorship Programmes: Lessons from a Critical Assessment of English Soccer. *Journal of Advertising Research*, 45(3), 328-338.
6. Clemes, M. D., Brush, G. J., Collins, M. J. (2011). Analysing the Professional Sports Experience: A Hierarchical Approach. *Sports Management Review*, 14, 370-388.
7. Collignon, H. & Sultan, N. (2014). Winning in Business Sports. *ATKeaney Report*. (2016, October 08). Retrieved from:

- <https://www.atkearney.com/documents/10192/5258876/Winning+in+the+Business+of+Sports.pdf/ed85b644-7633-469d-8f7a-99e4a50aad8>.
8. Collignon, H., Sultan, N. & Santander, C. (2011). The Sports Market: Major Trends and Challenges in an Industry Full of Passion. ATKearney Report. (2016, October 08). Retrieved from: http://www.smri.in/wp-content/uploads/2015/02/Sports_Market.pdf.
 9. ESPN Brasil (2017). Palmeiras foi o Clube Brasileiro que mais Faturou em 2016; Flamengo, o mais Equilibrado. (2017, June 17), Retrieved from: http://espn.uol.com.br/noticia/680873_palmeiras-foi-clube-brasileiro-que-mais-faturou-em-2016-flamengo-o-mais-equilibrado.
 10. Foster, G., O'Reilly, N. & Dávila, A (2016). Sports Business Management: Decision Making Around the Globe. New York, USA: Routledge.
 11. Fullerton, S. & Merz, G. R. (2008). The Four Domains of Sports Marketing: A Conceptual Framework. Sports Marketing Quarterly. 17(2), 90-108.
 12. Giroux, M., Pons, F. & Maltese, L. (2017). The Role of Perceived Brand Personality in Promotion Effectiveness and Brand Equity Development of Professional Sports Teams. International Journal of Sports Marketing and Sponsorship, 18(2), 180-195.
 13. Globo Esporte (2017). Público dos Estádios no Brasil em 2017. (2017, June 20). Retrieved from: <http://app.globoesporte.globo.com/futebol/publico-no-brasil/>.
 14. KPMG Report (2014). Business of Sports: Shaping a Successful Innings for the Indian Sports Industry (2016, October 08). Retrieved from: <http://www.smri.in/wp-content/uploads/2015/02/Business-of-Sports-KPMG.pdf>.
 15. Lance! & IBOPE (Instituto Brasileiro de Opinião e Estatística) (2017). As Maiores Torcidas de Futebol do Brasil. (2017, June 17). Retrieved from: <http://www.lance.com.br/futebol-nacional/flamengo-segue-com-maior-torcida-mas-vantagem-para-timao-cai.html>.
 16. Leopkey, B. & Parent, M. (2009). Risk Management Issues in Large-Scale Sporting Events: A Stakeholder Perspective. European Sports Management Quarterly, 9(2), 187-208.
 17. Maltese, L. & Danglade, J. P. (2014). Marketing du Sports et Événementiel Sportif. Paris: Dunod.
 18. McHugh, J., Bronson, P. & Watters, E. [Eds] (2015). The Future of Sports. Reports. futureof.com (2016, October 20). Retrieved from: <http://www.gannett-cdn.com/usatoday/editorial/sports/The-Future-of-Sports-2015-Report.pdf>
 19. Norris, J. I., Wann, D. L. & Zapalac, R. K. (2014). Sports fan Maximizing: Following the Best Team or Being the Best Fan? Journal of Consumer Marketing, 32(3), 157-166.
 20. Piipponen, H. (2011). Enhancing Customer Relations in Team Sports Business. Thesis (Master in Marketing). Department of Marketing and Management – School of Economics, Aalto University, Helsinki, Finland.
 21. Ratten, V. (2016). The Dynamics of Sports Marketing. Suggestions for Marketing Intelligence and planning. Marketing Intelligence & Planning, 14(2), 162-168.

22. Rundh, B. & Gottfridsson, P. (2015). Delivering Sports Events: The Arena Concept in Sports from Network Perspective. *Journal of Business & Industrial Marketing*, 30(7), 785-794.
23. São Paulo Official Website (2017). (2017, June 20). Retrieved from: <http://www.saopaulofc.net/noticias/noticias/historia/2015/12/30/historico-todos-os-titulos!>
24. Shilbury, D. (2009). *Sports Management Series*, 3 ed. Sydney: Allen & Unwin.
25. Storm, R. K., Wagner, U. & Nielsen, K. (2017). When Sports Meets Business: A Brief Introduction. In: Nielsen, K.; Wagner, U. & Storm, R. K. *When Sports Meets Business: Capabilities, Challenges, Critiques*. London, UK: Sage.
26. UOL (Universo Online) & Netshoes (2017, October 10). Quem Vende mais Camisas no Brazil. Retrieved from: <http://blogdojuca.uol.com.br/2017/09/quem-vende-mais-camisas-no-brasil/>
27. Yoshida, M. & James, J. D. (2010). Customer Satisfaction with Game and Service Experiences: Antecedents and Consequences. *Journal of Sports Management*, 24, 338-361.
28. Yoshida, M. (2017). Consumer Experience Quality: A Review and Extension of the Sports Management Literature. *Sports Management Review*, 20, 427-442.

Appendix

Programa de Pós-Doutorado em Administração

Objetivo: Este estudo visa compreender e analisar quais são os atributos dos torcedores que mais interferem em suas percepções com relação ao ecossistema esportivo do **São Paulo** para eventos esportivos.

Cabeçalho

Sexo () feminino () masculino	Renda Média (quantidade em salários mínimos) _____ salários mínimos (* salário mínimo no país: R\$ 880,00)
Presença no Estádio do seu Time () 1 vez ao mês () 2 – 3 vezes ao mês () 4 – 6 vezes ao mês	Transporte mais utilizado para ir ao Estádio () transporte público (ônibus, trem e/ou metrô) () transporte privado (táxi, fretamento) () veículo próprio (automóvel, motocicleta ou bicicleta)

Corpo do Questionário

Caro pesquisado, por favor, preencha o questionário abaixo com um **X**, a partir das seguintes instruções:

- (1) discordo totalmente. (3) não sei afirmar (5) concordo totalmente.
 (2) discordo em partes. (4) concordo em partes.

Os campeonatos, ligas e torneios dos quais o “meu time” participa têm...	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
(01) regulamentos claros, conhecidos e apoiados por torcedores, jogadores e mídias.					
(02) datas e horários inadequados ao torcedor que deseja assistir às partidas no estádio.					
(03) datas e horários adequados ao torcedor que assiste às partidas pela televisão.					
(04) jogos disputados, de qualidade e com lances que demonstram a técnica dos jogadores.					
(05) times equilibrados, o que não permite prever de antemão o possível campeão.					
(06) a atenção das mídias nas coberturas dos jogos (televisão, Internet, rádio, jornal, etc.).					
(07) jogos que são transmitidos para outros países na América do Sul e Europa.					
(08) 15.000 torcedores em média por jogo (30.000 é a média das ligas europeias).					
(09) tem a minha audiência em todas as rodadas, seja presente no estádio ou na televisão.					
(10) prêmios em dinheiro aos clubes participantes, condizentes com aos das ligas europeias.					

Quando o “meu time” joga “em casa” (ou em seu estádio), o clube...	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
(11) dispõe de vários pontos de venda (físicos e virtuais) de ingressos aos torcedores.					
(12) oferece assentos confortáveis e sanitários limpos e higienizados aos torcedores.					
(13) não disponibiliza estacionamentos de fácil acesso aos torcedores.					
(14) vende lanches e bebidas com preços condizentes aos praticados fora do estádio.					
(15) privilegia mais os Sócio-Torcedores do que os torcedores comuns na venda de ingressos.					
(16) não disponibiliza áreas de acessibilidades aos portadores de deficiências físicas.					
(17) faz parceria com o setor público para garantir transportes acessíveis aos torcedores.					
(18) garante a segurança dos torcedores no acesso e na saída do estádio.					
(19) disponibiliza funcionários para auxiliar e orientar os torcedores dentro do estádio.					
(20) disponibiliza ingressos com preços elevados em setores mais confortáveis do estádio.					
(21) dispõe de quiosques com variedade de produtos licenciados do clube para venda.					
(22) dispõe de quiosques para informar os benefícios de serviços aos Sócio-Torcedores.					

Com relação aos produtos e/ou serviços licenciados do “meu time”	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
(23) eu não os compro, porque eles são “caros”; eu compro produtos “piratas”.					
(24) eu não os compro, porque não há descontos aos Sócio-Torcedores.					
(25) eu não os compro, porque não há modelos e tamanhos apropriados a mim.					
(26) eu compro em média 3 produtos ou souvenirs do clube por ano.					
(27) eu os compro somente nas lojas licenciadas do clube.					
(28) eu os compro em lojas esportivas (ex. Centauro), porque não há muitas lojas do clube.					
(29) eu não os compro, porque há poucas opções de produtos, somente camisetas e bonés.					
(30) eu gostaria de comprar produtos “retros” como os nomes dos meus ídolos do passado.					
(31) eu não os compro, porque eu não gosto de patrocinadores estampados nos produtos.					
(32) eu gostaria de comprar em lojas no estádio, ao ingressar ou sair dos jogos.					
(33) eu gosto de comprar camisetas comemorativas ou o terceiro uniforme do clube.					
(34) eu já comprei para presentear meus familiares, amigos e colegas do					

trabalho.					
(35) eu não consigo customizar (ou personalizar) alguns produtos do clube.					

Como um torcedor do “meu time”...	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
(36) eu adoro ler livros, jornais e revistas que relatem a história do meu time.					
(37) eu adoro colecionar fotos e pôsteres do “meu time”.					
(38) eu assino Pay Per View (PPV) para assistir aos jogos e ajudar o “meu time”.					
(39) eu nunca visitei a sala de troféus para conhecer as conquistas do meu clube.					
(40) eu conheço os principais jogadores e sei dizer qual é o time titular.					
(41) eu visito, ao menos uma vez por semana, o site oficial do meu clube.					
(42) eu assisto aos treinos, ao menos uma vez ao mês.					
(43) eu sigo e monitoro os jogadores do “meu time” no Twitter e Facebook.					
(44) eu vou sempre às lojas do clube para conhecer os novos produtos e promoções.					
(45) eu tenho camisetas de diversas fases e períodos da história do “meu time”.					
(46) eu assisto as partidas do “meu time” quando ele vai jogar nos estádios dos adversários.					
(47) eu já influenciei familiares: esposa, marido e filhos (as) a torcerem pelo “meu time”.					
(48) eu já influenciei amigos (as) e colegas de trabalho a torcerem pelo “meu time”.					
(49) eu sempre visto a camiseta do “meu time” em suas partidas.					
(50) eu já vi pessoas usando a camiseta do “meu time” em outros Estados em que visitei.					
(51) eu já vi pessoas usando a camiseta do “meu time” em outros países em que visitei.					
(52) eu uso as redes sociais para “gozar” os adversários e defender o “meu time”.					
(53) eu assisto os programas esportivos diários para saber informações do “meu time”.					
(54) eu sempre seleciono o “meu time” no vídeo game FIFA.					
(55) eu acesso ao YouTube para rever os gols e as jogadas do “meu time”.					

A gestão do “meu time” ...	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
(56) é profissional, com aplicação de técnicas e práticas de gestão empresarial.					
(57) é transparente, pois presta contas das ações e tomadas de decisões no clube.					
(58) é responsável, uma vez que “não gasta mais do que recebe”.					
(59) não tem profissionais orientados ao torcedor-consumidor.					

(60) está em ordem, com relação ao pagamento dos jogadores e demais funcionários.					
(61) tem feito acordo com parceiros e patrocinadores lucrativos ao clube.					
(62) tem a preocupação de assegurar uma imagem positiva para atrair novos investidores.					
(63) valoriza os jogadores da base do clube como uma fonte de recursos e receitas futuras.					
(64) é alvo de críticas por não gerir o clube como uma visão voltada ao futuro.					
(65) investe em programas de responsabilidade social para elevar a imagem do clube.					
(66) procura desenvolver um relacionamento saudável com os seus torcedores.					
(67) a partir do marketing e da comunicação, tem procurado conhecer os torcedores.					

Com relação às empresas (patrocinadores, marcas esportivas, lojas, investidores, etc) ...	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
(68) elas não têm investido no "meu time".					
(69) elas têm agregado valor à marca do "meu clube".					
(70) elas têm poucos incentivos do governo para investir em meu clube.					
(71) elas têm receio de que a gestão do "meu clube" possa comprometer as suas marcas.					
(72) elas têm ajudado a melhorar a qualidade dos produtos e/ou serviços do clube.					
(73) elas têm ajudado a melhorar a relação entre clube e torcedor.					

Com relação às mídias no Brasil...	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
(74) elas valorizam mais os campeonatos nacionais do que os internacionais.					
(75) elas pagam o mesmo valor de direitos aos jogos que as mídias europeias aos clubes.					
(76) elas são "clubistas", cobre e transmite mais informações de um clube do que de outro.					
(77) elas promovem o naming rights dos parceiros do clube para encorajar investimentos.					
(78) elas interferem e definem os calendários de jogos no país.					

Desde já nós agradecemos a sua participação na pesquisa a sua contribuição foi de grande valia para o estudo.

Cordialmente, Prof. Dr. Edson Coutinho

Post Doctorate in Business Management | Marketing Programme

Objective This research aims to understand and analyse which fans' attributes most inferences in their view concerning the sports ecosystem of the **São Paulo Football Club** for sporting events.

Fan' Details

<p>Gender ☐ female ☐ male</p> <p>Monthly attendance in the stadium ☐ once a month ☐ 2 – 3 times per month ☐ 4 – 6 times per month</p>	<p>Monthly Salary (quantity of minimum salary) _____ minimum salary (*) minimum salary US \$ 280,00 (as a reference)</p> <p>Form of transport most used to go to the stadium ☐ public service (bus, train, subway) ☐ private service (taxi, Uber) ☐ own vehicle (car, Motorcycle, bicycle)</p>
---	--

Body of the Questionnaire

Dear fan, please, answer the questionnaire below by checking **X** respecting the following instructions.

- | | | |
|-----------------------------|----------------------------|--------------------------|
| (1) totally disagree | (3) I cannot answer | (5) totally agree |
| (2) partly disagree | (4) agree | |

The leagues and tournaments have...	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
(01) clear rules and regulation to guide fans and spectators;					
(02) appropriate date and time for the fans to watch the matches broadcast on tv;					
(03) appropriate date and time to watch the matches in the stadium;					
(04) high level of quality of games as well as competitive teams that demonstrate the player's technique and talent;					
(05) balanced teams that do not permit to predict the winner who will win;					
(06) draw the attention of the media (television, Internet and the radio) to broadcast the games;					
(07) matches that are broadcasted to other countries in South America and Europe;					
(08) 15,000 fans on average per game (30,000 is the average of the European leagues);					
(09) my attention (as a fan) in all rounds of the league, either in the stadium or on tv;					
(10) cash prizes to the sports club similar to European leagues, in general.					

When the team that I support plays in its stadium...	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
(11) there are several points of sale to buy tickets;					
(12) there are comfortable seats and toilets, cleaned and sanitised					
(13) it offers accessible parking for cars;					
(14) it sells snacks and drinks at honest prices;					

(15) prioritises members over ordinary fans when the sports club sells tickets;					
(16) does not provide accessibility areas (or seats) for disabled people;					
(17) develops the partnership with the public sector to ensure accessible transportation to the fans;					
(18) guarantees the safety of the fans at the pre, during and post-game;					
(19) provides employees to assist and guide the fans within the stadium;					
(20) delivers high ticket prices in several comfortable sectors within the arena;					
(21) has kiosks with an assortment of licensed goods for sale;					
(22) offers kiosks to promote the benefits of a range of services to the member.					

Regarding the licensed club's goods and services...	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
(23) I do not buy them because they are expensive, I buy a copy or an illegal good;					
(24) I do not buy them since there are no discounts to the members;					
(25) I do not buy them because there are not a lot of options and an appropriate size for me;					
(26) I buy on average 3 goods or souvenirs of the club every year;					
(27) I buy them only at licensed club's stores;					
(28) I buy them in sports stores (e.g. Decathlon) since there are not many club's stores;					
(29) I do not buy them since there are few good options, only T-shirts and caps;					
(30) I would like to buy vintage goods that remind me of former idol athletes from the remarkable past;					
(31) I do not buy them because I do not like the sponsor stamped on the club's goods;					
(32) I would like to buy goods from the stores in the stadium when I arrive or before I leave the stadium;					
(33) I want to buy T-shirts that celebrate club's achievements or the third club's uniform;					
(34) I already bought a good to give as a gift to my relatives, friends and co-workers;					
(35) I cannot customise some club's goods.					

As a fan of the team...	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
(36) I love reading books, newspapers, and magazines about the team;					
(37) I love collecting photos and posters of my team;					
(38) I subscribe to pay- tv to watch the games and help my team;					
(39) I have never been to the trophy room to know the achievements of the team;					
(40) I can identify and recognise the main athletes and I know those who usually play in every match;					

(41) I visit, at least once a week, the club's official website;					
(42) I attend the training, at least once a month;					
(43) I follow and like the players posts on Twitter and Facebook;					
(44) I always go to the club stores to familiarise with the new goods and promotions;					
(45) I have t-shirts from several periods of my team history;					
(46) I attend the matches of my team when they play in the opponent's stadium;					
(47) I have already encouraged my relatives to support the team who I am a fan;					
(48) I have already encouraged friends and co-workers to cheer for my team;					
(49) I have always worn my team's t-shirt at their games;					
(50) I have seen people wearing my team's t-shirt in other States or provinces I have visited;					
(51) I have seen people wearing my team's t-shirt in another country I have visited;					
(52) I use social networks to mock my friends who support the opponent teams and to defend my team;					
(53) I have watched daily sports tv programmes to get updated on information about my team;					
(54) I always choose my team in FIFA video game;					
(55) I always access YouTube to watch the goals and matches of my team.					

The management of the club...	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
(56) is professional since managers use business management principles;					
(57) is transparent seeing that it executes accountability, and decision-making in the club;					
(58) is responsible, inasmuch as the managers only invest money and resources that are available;					
(59) does not have professionals who develop principles that approach customer-orientation;					
(60) can pay its bills, athletes, employees, and other investments;					
(61) has established partnerships with attractive companies;					
(62) seeks to ensure a positive image to the club in view to get more investments;					
(63) invests in athletes produced by the club in order to sell them to get profit in the future business;					
(64) receives criticisms for managing the club not in line with new management trends;					
(65) invests in social responsibility programmes to enhance the image of the club;					
(66) aims to build a healthy relationship with fans;					
(67) practices marketing and communication strategies to meet its fans' expectations.					

Regarding the partners and sponsors...	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
(68) they have invested more resources and money into the club;					
(69) they have added value to the club brand;					
(70) they have little support from the Brazilian government to invest money in sports;					
(71) they suspect that the mismanagement of the sports club might damage their brands;					
(72) they have incremented the quality of club's goods and services;					
(73) they have enhanced the relationship between club and fans.					

The media...	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
(74) value more the national leagues and tournaments than the international ones;					
(75) pay an amount of money to buy rights to broadcast games, as the European media do;					
(76) broadcast and publish more information about one club than others;					
(77) promote the sponsor naming rights in order to encourage new investments to the club;					
(78) and interfere on the leagues or tournaments to define the matches calendar.					

Creative Commons licensing terms

Authors will retain copyright to their published articles agreeing that a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) terms will be applied to their work. Under the terms of this license, no permission is required from the author(s) or publisher for members of the community to copy, distribute, transmit or adapt the article content, providing a proper, prominent and unambiguous attribution to the authors in a manner that makes clear that the materials are being reused under permission of a Creative Commons License. Views, opinions and conclusions expressed in this research article are views, opinions and conclusions of the author(s). Open Access Publishing Group and European Journal of Management and Marketing Studies shall not be responsible or answerable for any loss, damage or liability caused in relation to/arising out of conflict of interests, copyright violations and inappropriate or inaccurate use of any kind content related or integrated on the research work. All the published works are meeting the Open Access Publishing requirements and can be freely accessed, shared, modified, distributed and used in educational, commercial and non-commercial purposes under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).